
IMPACT MEASUREMENT OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION TRAINING MODULE ON CIVIL SERVANT CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT: A CASE OF BANGLADESH CIVIL SERVICE

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Abstract

Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre (BPATC) has the mandate to impart career training for civil servants of Bangladesh. The Foundation Training Course (FTC) is one of the most important civil servant capacity-building courses. As a 'Centre of Excellence, BPATC plays an active role in mitigating human resources demand at the national level to provide effective, inclusive, self-mandated, and personalized training for the public sector in Bangladesh. Therefore, the study aims to determine how satisfied trainees are in terms of receiving skill, knowledge, and attitude; to identify training modules contained in terms of must know, should know and nice to know, and assess modules' impact on capacity development for the civil servants. A structured questionnaire was administered for data collection from the trainees who participated in the P-63rd FTC at BPATC to achieve research objectives. The 'Public Administration' training module has four sub-modules and module contents have given reliability validation that shows training contents as per module items were internally consistent at the level of satisfaction. The descriptive statistics results and the frequency per cent results have shown that trainees are somehow satisfied with the recipient of training at BPATC. Again, the significant finding has shown which contents must know and should know for fostering competencies in liquidating their quotidian activities. This research has also done Pearson correlation and ANOVA, regression with the coefficient result, and found that the regression model is significant and explains 40.1% of the total variance. Moreover, public sector management; and 'integrity in public administration' sub-modules of public administration have a significant impact on the capacity development of civil servants to discharge their duties in service life. Lastly, a policy suggestion is drawn for the curriculum committee to redesign training curricula and their delivery method, particularly for public servants, as a tool for human resource development.

Key words: Impact Measurement, Public Administration Module, Civil Service Training, Capacity Development, Bangladesh.

Introduction

The effectiveness of an organization's performance is hooked on the employee training of those who perform the duties and responsibilities of the organization (Samwel, 2018). Civil service is considered the superior service, and civil servants are responsible for delivering government services to the citizens of the country. The patterns of civil services are in British shape, especially in South Asia, because of colonial rule (Wilson, 2007). Still, civil servants are amazingly trained in several essentials and contemporary national and international affairs. However, the Bangladesh Public Administration Centre (BPATC) is the highest civil service training institution in Bangladesh,

popularly known as the apex training organization (Islam & Hossain, 2019). It was established in 1984 as an autonomous body to prepare future leaders and policymakers having a varied understanding of diverse social, economic, political, environmental, scientific, and organizational aspects involved in planning national policies and strategies (BPATC, 2019). One of BPATC's crucial missions is to build a group of talented and professional human resources by conveying high-quality training and development opportunities (Islam & Hosen, 2021).

Besides, Bangladesh has a blueprint for triumphing the dream trajectory. It has planned to reach the middle-income country by achieving 'vision 2021', become an upper-middle-income country by succeeding SDG-2030 (UN, 2015), and become a developed nation by attaining 'vision 2041'. Thus, the government has already approved numerous plans and development strategies to achieve the targets, where skilled and trained human resources (UN, 2013) are required especially, civil servants. The government remains to implement excellent training and learning activities for developing officials to deliver better public services. In this case, the BPATC provides multiple training modules and contents for massive change to the trainee's performance and knowledge (Hossain & Islam, 2020). Indeed, effective training has the essential power to upsurge the knowledge, skills, and abilities of the employees (Lindsey, King, Hebl, & Levine, 2015), which will ultimately and positively change the organization's performance (Salah, 2016; Becker & Huselid, 1998; Khan, 2012). Nevertheless, need-based training is crucial for enhancing organizational performance, especially trainee's performance, and development. In fact, effective training assists the trainee, and their institutions upgrade their performance and outcome (Bhatti, Battour, Sundram, & Otham, 2013).

The research was based on the public administration modules of the FTC of newly recruited civil servants of the country. Consequently, the study intends to determine how satisfied trainees are in terms of receiving skill, knowledge, and attitude; to identify training modules containing requirements in terms of must know, should know, and nice to know; and assess modules' impact on capacity development for the civil servants. As a final point, the research suggests future directions for re-designing training modules and contents. The paper has been constructed with an introduction study objectives, concept, public administration module description, materials, methods, data presentation and analysis, and concluding remarks.

Theoretical background

Conceptual Explanation of Public Administration Training Module for Capacity Development of Civil Servant

Most of the entry-level civil servants work in the field of administration at the operational level. These entry-level civil servants are government agents who deliver services to the citizens of Bangladesh. The governmental system and laws; public service management; child rights, gender development; and integrity in public administration are all subunits of the public administration module. In local-level public administration, related departments and organizations are providing services to the citizens of Bangladesh.

1 Government System and Essential Laws

Bangladesh is a parliamentary democratic country in the Westminster style (Ahmed, 2011). The Prime Minister is the head of the government, whereas the President is the head of the state (Moniruzzaman, 2009). The Bangladeshi government is divided into three branches: the executive branch, the legislative branch, and the judicial branch (Halim, 2008). To begin with, Bangladesh's legislature, known as Sangsad (Parliament), is unicameral. The Speaker is the chairperson of the parliament house. There are 300 members of parliament (MPs), with 50 reserved seats for women (Chowdhury, 2013). The significant role of this house is to make and amend laws for the country

(Parliament, 1972). Second, the executive branch is in charge of putting the government's rules, regulations, ordinances, missions, and visions into action to benefit the general public (Halim, 2008). The Prime Minister is the constitutional leader of the executive body (Secretariat, 2020). Finally, the judicial branch has been established with an apex Supreme Court made up of the Appellate Division and High Court Division (Halim, 2008). The District Courts, City Criminal Courts, Specialized Courts, and Tribunals are all connected to the country's judicial system, and all are a lower grade of the Supreme Court (Banglapedia, 2015).

Thus, the expected objectives from this module are to learn about Bangladesh's governmental structure and how to manage public offices and examine the contents of the constitution and essential legislation and how they are applied in office operations.

2 Public Service Management

As a nonprofit organization, public service is intended to serve the country's citizen (Frank & Lewis, 2004). The government usually provides it to the general public who live within its jurisdiction. Thus, public service management is considered to coordinate and organize the execution procedures of public services (Bryson & George, 2020). According to Whitfield (2001), "Public Service Management is designed to be good quality public management practice. The aim is to define a practice which fully reflects the principles and values of public service ethos, and which is free of gimmicks and fading or new fads" (Whitfield, 2001). Better public services require both public service ethics and public service management (Chapman, 1993). However, under the transformative wave of changing environments with a modern paradigm (Clarke & Clegg, 1999) and pandemic circumstances like COVID-19 (Islam, Talukder, Siddiqui, & Islam, 2020), public service management evolves.

Therefore, the goals of this module are to improve the ability to deal with the issues of public service delivery; to engage employees about the role of civil service in the context of national and global levels and to identify governance issues, solve problems and seek innovation to enhance better public service delivery mechanisms.

3 Child Rights, Gender & Development

The most vulnerable members of society are children and women (Carpenter, 2005). It has been noted that they are frequently overlooked in a country's development procedures. It is essential to formulate gender and child-specific development policies, guidelines, advocacy tools, strategies, and plans. Indeed, human security and child rights have become urgent due to the various vulnerabilities, mistreatment, and lack of agencies for millions of children, particularly in poor and underdeveloped countries (Pink, 2012). The government, NGOs, Civil Society, and development partners all have a responsibility to guarantee children's and women's rights. It has been said that "gender equality and women's empowerment is the outcome of an expansion in women's freedom and the ability to choose a way of life they value" (Abbott & Teti, 2016). In most cases, women's and gender development can be approached in a variety of ways. According to research, the approach recognizes women as active participants in action, having both a productive and reproductive function (Mitchell, 1996).

Thus, the module's objectives are captured to enable the participants to identify and assess current societal challenges affecting males and females and highlight interventions required to protect women's and children's rights.

4 Integrity in Public Administration

Integrity has become a popular concept in government and governance studies and actual policymaking at all levels (Huberts, 2018). It has been considered that the term 'integrity has been introduced into public services to combat corruption (Kouzmin, 2010) and ensure transparency and

accountability. Public officials should communicate with the general public, businesses, and other government agencies professionally. The public administration must preserve integrity and honesty in its activities to fight against corruption and enhance the general public's trust in the government. Bangladesh's government has launched the National Integrity Strategy (NIS) to ensure that public services are free of corruption (GoB, 2012). Thus, integrity must assure accountability, transparent procedures, competency systems, and reactive and proactive anti-corruption measures from the standpoint of the rule of law (Aulich et al., 2012).

Thus, at the end of the training program, trainees would be able to understand the responsibility of using public power for public interests; to carry out duties with honesty and integrity so that transparency can be established in the decision-making process; and avoid and address inappropriate behavior, conduct, and disclosure of facts without concealing and distorting them in public affairs.

5 Capacity Development of the Civil Servants

Civil servants have been receiving training from various training organizations. The majority of the training programs are skill-oriented, which benefits public servants and organizations in the long run (Becker & Huselid, 1998). BPATC organizes training for civil servants (Islam & Hossain, 2019; Islam, Arifuzzaman, & Fatema, 2012), which helps them to improve job knowledge, skill, and attitude (Perloff, 2016; Baldwin & Ford, 1988); enhance visionary outlook; develop peer relationship (Powell, 2011); improve communication power (Arefin & Islam, 2018); understanding various rules, laws, regulations to perform duties; and as a whole understanding role of a civil servant. Participants of FTC are newcomers to the civil service; as a result, BPATC's primary responsibility is to improve their enhancing capacity in terms of skill, knowledge, and attitude toward work culture. The FTC curriculum is developed in such a manner that by the end of the course trainees will have a better understanding of office procedures, customs, and values, as well as improve their knowledge and skills as office managers. More significantly, they improved their positive attitude toward citizen service delivery and communication conduct due to this training. Civil servants develop themselves by receiving training in these areas. Therefore, these sub-modules of training are used as measuring indicators of employee development.

Materials and Methods

1 Participants and Research Design

BPATC offers various training courses, with the Foundation Training Course being one of the most important for entry-level cadre officers. As a residential training program, FTC has a set of modules and a certain length of time. A unique survey questionnaire tool was used for this study purpose at the end of the P-63rd Foundation Training Course. Only a quantitative approach was utilized in this research (Saunders et al. 2009), and primary and secondary data were used. 265 trainees out of 319 replied to the questionnaire survey procedures, including 72 females and 193 males from 14 different cadres of delegates among the respondents. Overall, their length of service was not exceeding five years, and the majority were within three years.

2 Sample Size

The population for this research was those who had attended the P-63 Foundation Training Course at BPATC. They were purposively chosen and distributed a structured questionnaire, and finally, 265 valid filled-in questionnaires were received. Therefore, the sample size was determined and followed by Yamne (1967).

Table 1: Respondents Cadre Distribution with Gender Frequency Distribution

Cadres	Male	Female	Total
BCS (Administration)	23	16	39
BCS (Police)	07	00	07
BCS (Ansar)	03	00	03
BCS (Foreign Affairs)	05	05	10
BJS (Judicial Service)	32	05	37
BCS (Statistics)	04	02	06
BCS (Information)	09	02	11
BCS (Fisheries)	36	08	44
BCS (Family Planning)	07	01	08
BCS (Taxation)	03	01	04
BCS (Livestock)	07	02	09
BCS (Public Works Division)	22	06	28
BCS (Agriculture)	33	23	56
BCS (Custom, &Excise)	02	01	03
Total	193	72	265

3.3 Reliability of Variables Items

There are four sub-modules of the public administration module as independent variables, where capacity development is considered as the dependent variable. Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the consistency of the module's measurement items, and it was discovered that the course modules items are remarkably consistent at a satisfactory level (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010). Thus, the course modules and their component association are given validation (coefficient). The results of the reliability test are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability Result

Modules (Variables)	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Government System and Essential Laws	13	.963
Public Service Management	11	.957
Child Rights, Gender & Development	8	.932
Integrity in Public Administration	6	.937
Capacity Development	7	.886

4 Module Content and Capacity Development Component Measurement

The sub-modules of public administration were measured with some specific items of training content. For instance, the 'governmental system and essential law' module was measured with thirteen items; the 'public service management' module was quantified with eleven items; 'child rights' module was computed with eight items; and 'integrity in public administration' module was measured with six items. In contrast, capacity development as a dependent variable was measured with seven items.

5 Components Statement and Scale

The contents of the sub-module of public administration are perceived in two distinct dimensions based on trainees' perspectives. On the left-hand side, the emphasis is on the categories of "Must Know", "Should Know", and "Nice to Know", ranging from "1" to "3". Require levels 'Must Know', 'Should Know', and 'Nice to Know' are measured with a frequency percentage value. On the right-hand side, Likert (1932) scale is regarded with "1" to "6", indicating a very low to an exceptional degree of learning. Here, 6=outstanding, 5=excellent, 4=High, 3=Moderate, 2= Average, 1=Very low. The measurement scale is used to assess knowledge of training contents. The learning level is

represented by descriptive values such as mean value and standard deviation.

6 Training Evaluation Kirkpatrick Model: Reaction and Learning Stages

As the respondents were the new entrants in civil service, thus the FTC was a career training course and a requirement for job confirmation. Supervisors customized the training materials and delivery methods depending on the trainees' job requirements. According to Kirkpatrick (1996), training evaluation is assessed with four dimensions: reaction; Learning; Behavior, and Result (Kirkpatrick, 1996; Smidt, Balandin, Sigafos, & A.Reed, 2009). Even so, the emphasis in this research is on reaction and learning rather than behavior and result.

Result and Discussion

After entering 265 valid data, the SPSS was utilized to generate the outcome. The public administration training module and its sub-modules and capacity development as a dependent variable module were used to create descriptive statistics. Subsequently, a higher-level statistical analysis was performed to determine the impact of modules on the development of civil servant capacity.

1 Government System and Essential Laws

Civil servants must understand how government systems function and the rules, regulations, and laws that govern their jobs. The government system and essential laws module is delivered with various topics or contents, developed by the Ministry of Public Administration with germane proficiency. As the research was focused on the reaction and learning level of training evaluation, the level of learning is presented with descriptive values such as mean value and standard deviation result (Table 3).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Governmental System and Essentials Laws Module

Level of Requirement			Items	Level of Learning	
NK% (f)	SK% (f)	MK% (f)	Module topics/items	Mean	SD
4.2(11)	25.7(68)	70.2(186)	Salient Features of Bangladesh Constitution	3.90	1.480
1.5(4)	21.9(58)	76.6(203)	Legislature of Bangladesh	3.73	1.363
3.0(8)	22.3(59)	74.7(198)	Judiciary of Bangladesh	3.77	1.417
4.9(13)	27.9(74)	67.2(178)	Executive of Bangladesh	3.77	1.379
6.4(17)	24.2(64)	69.4(184)	Interrelation of Legislature, Judiciary & Executive	3.71	1.286
5.7(15)	27.7(73)	66.8(177)	Local Government System and Decentralization in Bangladesh	3.64	1.337
13.2(35)	22.6(60)	64.2(170)	Local Govt. and Development	3.51	1.399
10.2(27)	21.1(56)	68.7(182)	The Mobile Court Act, 2009	3.66	1.632
10.2(27)	21.1(56)	68.7(182)	Overview of Land Management: Mutation, Land Dispute, Land Records	3.48	1.523
15.8(42)	26.4(70)	57.7(153)	Rules of Business & Allocation of Business	3.97	1.531
10.9(35)	27.2(72)	61.9(164)	Penal Code: Essential Sections	3.57	1.439
14.3(38)	19.2(51)	66.4(186)	Laws of Inheritance (Muslim and Hindu)	3.55	1.365
18.5(49)	23.8(63)	57.7(153)	The Public Demand Recover Act, 1913	3.50	1.453

There are 13 topics in this module, and respondents claimed that they are all required for them, mostly at the 'must know' level. Despite the fact that all cadres are not monitored and controlled by law and order like police and administration, thus, some respondents stated that 'should know', and very few claimed that 'nice to know'. Nevertheless, civil servants as a whole

should be familiar with rules and regulations as well as relevant legislation and how they are applied in the sphere of public administration. The reaction level varies from cadre to cadre or by the nature of the job, and data is often distributed rather than skewed. On the other side, when it comes to learning level, all of the items did not score a high mean value, which is close to the average (Table 3).

There is a mismatch between the degree of requirement and their learning level. As a result, training methods and delivery techniques need to be reorganized, modified, and redesigned.

2 Public Service Management

Managing public services is also one of the fundamental competencies of civil servants. Management tools, processes, and techniques are vital aspects of running a successful public administration. The paradigm of service delivery in public administration is changing practically every day, civil servants must simplify work processes and incorporate innovation into government. Thus, the principal essence of public service management is to provide civil servants with contemporary management tools and techniques such as change management, total quality management, and business process re-engineering to offer services from the administration organ.

The public service management module includes many themes and elements that were produced with the help of the Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre by the Ministry of Public Administration. As the nature of the job changes in response to the environment, so does the training intake required to keep up with new knowledge and skills. Therefore, the training material and technique are aligned with the current content and service delivery methodologies.

Due to the fact that all cadre are not controlled or monitored human and material resources in public administration, respondents stated that all eleven topics are necessary for them, mostly at the level of 'must know', although some claimed that 'should know', and just a few claimed that 'good to know'. For cadre officials, understanding public service management is essential, nevertheless, the individual concept of the module varies. As a result, reaction levels is mixed and vary from person to person depending on the nature of the job. Respondents diversely provided their thoughts regarding their reaction status according to the training assessment Kirkpatrick model (Table 4). They argue that when it comes to public service management training topics, must know has taken precedence over should know and nice to know.

On the other hand, when it comes to learning level, all of the items did not achieve a high mean (4.0; >3.0) value; instead, they were practically average (Table 4) with a high standard deviation. There is a mismatch between the degree of need and their learning level, resulting in a discrepancy or gap. As a result, training techniques and delivery systems need to be reorganized, modified, and redesigned.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Public Service Management

Level of Requirement			Items Module topics/items	Level of Learning	
NK% (f)	SK% (f)	MK% (f)		Mean	SD
12.5(33)	37.4(92)	50.2(133)	Essentials of Public Management	3.72	1.241
14.3(38)	31.1(109)	44.5(118)	Development Administration: Bangladesh Perspective	3.61	1.371
18.5(49)	39.6(105)	41.9(111)	NPM: Changing Dynamics of PSM	3.46	1.377
18.5(49)	43.0(114)	38.5(102)	Business Process Re-engineering	3.46	1.380
14.7(39)	24.2(64)	61.1(162)	Citizen Charter: Bangladesh Perspective	3.89	1.397
15.5(41)	43.3(91)	52.2(133)	Policy Process	3.57	1.378
18.5(50)	32.1(85)	49.4(131)	Problems of Policy Implementation	3.62	1.380
16.2(43)	27.5(73)	56.2(149)	Good Governance: Principles and Practices	3.79	1.391
15.1(40)	32.5(86)	52.5(139)	Total Quality Management	3.73	1.383
15.1(40)	27.2(72)	57.7(153)	Public Private Partnership (PPP)	3.79	1.349
19.6(52)	35.1(93)	45.3(120)	Strategic Management in Public Sector	3.61	1.286

3 Child Rights, Gender & Development

Trainees have undergone a module on child rights, gender, and development as part of the Foundation Training Course, which is incorporated into the public administration training module. Bangladesh is described as a densely populated nation where child labour is prevalent in the car and readymade garment sectors. Gender equality is also prioritized in all parts of life, including jobs and revenue-generating enterprises. As a result, government officials must be knowledgeable in these areas in order to handle child concerns and create a gender-friendly working environment.

The public administration module's "child labor, gender, and development" sub-module is assessed using eight themes or questions. Considering the demographic distribution, it is essential to understand gender and its implications for women's development. In Bangladesh, children are enrolled in the labour force after 15 years. The government machinery is devoted to the development of children, and those institutions are managed and administrated by civil servants. As a result, civil servant capacity development is crucially significant.

More than half of the young civil servants believe that civil servants must understand gender (52.8 percent), legal issues affecting women and children (60.8 percent), children's status (58.1 percent), children's welfare activities (52.1 percent), the role of working women (61.9 percent), and women's challenges (58.9 percent). However, the 'Should Know' scale percent values are over 20%, and the 'Nice to Know' scale percent values are over 13%. The contents in this module seem to have importance on 'Must Know' percent value, whereas the 'Nice to Know' percent value isn't the highest (Table 5).

The learning levels from the training course in those module subjects, on the other hand, are closer to 4.0 as a mean value out of 6.0 (Table 5), indicating a gap or disparity. As a result, the method of delivery or techniques for trainees' attachment to presenting subjects must be modified per the learning goals or satisfaction of the trainees.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics on Child Rights, Gender and Development

Level of Requirement			Items	Level of Learning	
NK% (f)	SK% (f)	MK% (f)	Module topics/items	Mean	SD
21.1(56)	24.9(66)	52.8(140)	Gender: Conceptual Aspects	3.90	1.252
15.1(40)	24.2(64)	60.8(161)	Women and Child Rights: Legal Coverage in Bangladesh	3.98	1.281
16.6(44)	24.9(66)	58.1(1)	Situation of Children in Bangladesh	3.75	1.201
13.6(36)	34.3(91)	52.1(138)	Activities Taken for Child Welfare: Effectiveness and Monitoring System	3.71	1.204
17.0(45)	21.1(56)	61.9(164)	Role of Women in Development	4.03	1.131
17.4(46)	23.8(63)	58.9(156)	Challenges of Working Women	3.76	1.408
14.7(39)	34.0(90)	51.3(136)	CEDAW: Bangladesh Perspective	3.65	1.317
13.6(36)	31.7(84)	54.7(145)	Women and Child Right Approaches	3.63	1.432

4 Integrity in Public Administration

In 2012, the Bangladesh government passed the National Integrity Strategy (NIS) to promote good governance (Hossain and Islam, 2020). Bangladesh's government has taken NIS literally to address corruption, as part of its plan to achieve the SDGs by 2030. Thus, the Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre included a training module on integrity in public administration intending to understand the responsibility of using public power for the public benefit; performing duties with honesty and integrity; and avoiding and addressing improper behavior and conduct at public offices and with service recipients.

The Integrity in Public Administration module is taught using a variety of subjects created by the Ministry of Public Administration and appropriate expertise from training institutions. According

to the participants (Table 6), module subjects are very much at the ‘must know’ level (more than 50% scored), while should know scored more than 22% and in certain cases, 42.3 percent, and nice to know scored more than 10%. On the other hand, Trainees appreciate the relevance of integrity in public administration and topics practices from the standpoint of service delivery. Integrity in public administration module themes earned a high mean of approximately 4.0 with significant standard deviation values compared to other sub-module subjects. However, more interactive engagement training approaches were necessary to absorb such concepts and their uses in public administration as a means of accountability and transparency.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics on Integrity Training Module

Level of Requirement			Items	Learning Level	
NK% (f)	SK% (f)	MK% (f)	Module topics/item	Mean	SD
12.8(34)	23.4(62)	63.8(169)	Introduction to Ethics, Values and Morality	4.01	1.535
16.6(44)	22.6(60)	60.8(161)	National Integrity Strategy (NIS)	3.92	1.525
13.2(35)	34.3(91)	52.5(139)	Human Rights and Access to Public Services	3.98	1.230
13.6(36)	21.1(56)	65.3(173)	Combating Corruption in Public Service Delivery	3.89	1.474
12.8(34)	42.3(112)	44.9(119)	Religious Values in Controlling Corruption	3.72	1.507
12.5(33)	22.6(60)	64.9(172)	Transparency and Accountability in Service Delivery	4.07	1.451

5 Capacity Development

Civil servants receive training from various institutions, and the majority of training programs are skill-oriented, enhancing their ability to fulfil official tasks. The capacity development of civil workers is assessed using seven criteria. BPATC, in particular, organizes training programs for career civil servants that help them improve job knowledge, skills, and attitudes. When comparing the mean value of each item to the descriptive statistical result, all of the items are rated higher than 4.0 on average, with a high standard deviation (Table 7). As a learning outcome, the result suggests that government servants are satisfied with their training program for capacity development.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics on Capacity Development

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Enhance my skill	265	1	6	4.05	1.357
Enhance my knowledge	265	1	6	4.38	1.324
Enhance my outlook	265	1	6	4.58	1.323
Enhance my coworker positive relationship behavior	265	1	6	4.27	1.348
Public speaking skill	265	1	6	4.46	1.206
Knowledge of rules, laws, and regulation	265	1	6	4.46	1.354
Understanding role of civil servant	265	1	6	4.18	1.461

6 Correlation Matrix among independents and dependent variables

This research included four independent variables (depending on the training module) and one dependent variable (capacity development for the civil servant). These four independent variables are the submodules of public administration, and their number of items is measured. Consequently, the study uses the Person correlation matrix with the dependent variable to examine the relationship between civil servant capacity development factors. The Pearson correlation results revealed that the training module as independent variables strongly and strongly associated with civil servant capacity development. Accordingly, the result shows (Table 8) that the public administration training module and its submodules are linked to civil servant capacity development.

Table 8: Pearson Correlation Matrix with Independent and Dependent Variables

Variables (DV & IV)	1	2	3	4	5
1. Governmental System and Essential Law	1	.785**	.699**	.600**	.490**
2. Public Service Management	.785**	1	.602**	.686**	.584**
3. Child Right & Gender Development	.699**	.602**	1	.528**	.389**
4. Integrity in Public Administration	.600**	.686**	.528**	1	.558**
5. Capacity Development	.490**	.584**	.389**	.558**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

7 Impact Measurement for Capacity Development of the Civil Servant

The Pearson correlation matrix has indicated that capacity development is interrelated to the government system, public service management, child rights and gender development, and public administration integrity. To assess the effects of those submodules on capacity development, an ANOVA (analysis of variance), regression model summary, and coefficient table are generated.

7.1 Regression Model Summary

To obtain the model summary, a simple regression was conducted in SPSS (Table 9). The government system, public service management, child rights, and integrity (as independent variables) are included in the model summary, whereas the dependent variable is capacity development in a civil servant. The model found significant ($p < .000$). There is a strong connection ($r = .633$) between all the predicted variables. With a high $F = 36.779$ value, the model R-square is .401, and the adjusted R-square is .390. As a result of the model, all of the anticipated variables have a 40.1 percent impact on capacity development. Finally, according to the modified R-square model, 39.0 percent of the total variation could be explained. As a consequence, the training modules and sub-module conclusions (government system, public service management, child rights, and integrity in public administration) have a positive and substantial influence on capacity development. Young civil servants' capacity for service delivery will be strengthened if they obtain training in the public administration module.

Table 9: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.633 ^a	.401	.390	.87956	.401	36.779	4	220	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Module13, Module12, Module10, Module11

Table 10: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	113.812	4	28.453	36.779	.000 ^b
	Residual	170.197	220	.774		
	Total	284.010	224			

a. Dependent Variable: Capacity Development CD

b. Predictors: (Constant), Module13, Module12, Module10, Module11

**Memo: Module 10= Governmental System and Essential Law; Module 11= Public Service Management; Module 12= Child Right & Gender Development; Module 13= Integrity in Public Administration

7.2 Coefficients result and impact measurement on capacity development

For this study, impact measurement and collinearity are performed. The model is significant, according to the ANOVA (Table 10) and regression model (Table 9). The model is composed of four predictor variables. The coefficients result revealed that all the predicted variables are not positive

and significantly impact civil servants' capacity development. Module 11 (public service management, as shown in Table 4) is the most important predictor module, accounting for 41.2 percent of the total variance, whereas module 13 (public administration integrity, as shown in Table 6) is substantial, contributing for 27.7% of the variance explained. Therefore, it is verified that the public service management module has an impact (41.2 percent, p.000) on civil servant capacity development, whereas the integrity in the public administration module has an impact (27.7%, p.000) on civil servant capacity development.

In contrast, other modules have a small but considerable influence on capacity development. Because of these courses and themes, trainees improved their capacity to perform their responsibilities and provide service to people. It has no collinearity problem, according to tolerance and VIF findings (Table 11). As a result, multicollinearity is not an issue in this research.

Table 11: Coefficient result and Impact Measurement on Dependent Variable and Collinearity Statistics

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.307	.230		5.680	.000		
Module10	-.011	.087	-.012	-.129	.898	.316	3.167
Module11	.404	.091	.412	4.429	.000	.314	3.184
Module12	.010	.081	.009	.120	.904	.462	2.163
Module13	.242	.065	.277	3.749	.000	.500	1.999

Dependent Variable: CD

Conclusions

The Ministry of Public Administration, which oversees human resource development, develops career training courses for public employees. The impact training program is a crucial component of government servant capacity building. Every training course comprises several modules, each of which has some subjects based on their relevance to the needs of the participants. However, this study aims to determine how satisfied trainees are in terms of receiving skill, knowledge, and attitude; to identify training module contains in terms of must know, should know, and nice to know; and to assess modules impact on capacity development for the civil servants. Only two phases, reaction and learning level, of the Kirkpatrick training assessment model were examined in this study. In terms of training material, the level of reaction is judged using the terms "must know", "should know", and "nice to know". On the other hand, learning level is assessed using a six-point Likert scale ranging from "very low" to "outstanding".

For impact measurement on capacity development, descriptive analysis such as frequency and percent value, mean value, standard deviation value, correlation, ANOVA and regression model, and coefficient value is used. The regression model was shown to be significant, explaining 40.1 percent of the total variance. As a result, the regression model revealed that predictor variables are strongly influenced by the public servant's ability development. Thus, capacity development is significantly impacted by the public administration module and sub-modules. More specifically, the findings of the coefficient table indicated that public service management and integrity in public administration training modules had a substantial influence on capacity development. Capacity development accounts for 41.2 percent of the total variance and 27.7 percent of the total variance is explained respectively.

According to the necessary level required, the 'must know' level did not exceed 70%, indicating that the material should be re-evaluated in light of the trainees' needs and work requirements. As a result, training and development requirements should be assessed. On the other

hand, the total mean score did not achieve a high level when assessing learning level by the mean value. As a result, training techniques must be redesigned following the training content and deliberation process for trainees to internalize information. By undertaking extensive study and consultation, the Ministry of Public Administration and the BPATC may work together to determine the training and development needs. This study employed a quantitative technique to record data, however, a qualitative approach may be applied in future investigations.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

References

- Abbott, P., & Teti, A. (2016). The Political, Social and Economic Drivers of the 2011 Egyptian Uprising. *Arab Transformations Project*. Retrieved July 27, 2020, Available from : <http://www.jstor.com/stable/resrep14104.7>
- Ahmed, N. (2011). Parliament and democratic consolidation in Bangladesh. *Australasian Parliamentary Review*, 26(2), 53-68.
- Arefin, S., & Islam, N. (2018). A study on the motivation to transfer training in the Banking Industry of Bangladesh. *South Asian Journal of Human Resources Management*, 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2322093718803210>.
- Aulich, C., Wettenhall, R., & Evans, M. (2012). Understanding integrity in public administration: Guest Editors' Introduction. *Policy Studies*, 33(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2011.635884>.
- Baldwin, T. T., & Ford, J. K. (1988). Training of training: A review and directions for future research. *Personnel Psychology*, 41, 63-105.
- Banglapedia. (2015, February 24). Judicial System. Available from : http://en.banglapedia.org/index.php?title=Judicial_System.
- Becker, B. E., & Huselid, M. A. (1998). High performance work systems and firm performance: A synthesis of research and managerial implications. *Research in Personnel and Human Resource Management*, 16, 53-101. Available from : https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313524630_High_performance_work_systems_and_firm_performance_A_synthesis_of_research_and_managerial_implications.
- Bhatti, M. A., Battour, M. M., Sundram, V. P., & Otham, A. A. (2013). Transfer of training: does it truly happen? An examination of support, instrumentality, retention and learner readiness on the transfer motivation and transfer of training. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 273-297. <https://doi.org/10.1108/0309059131131274>.
- BPATC. (2019). Annual Report 2018-2019. Savar, Dhaka: Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre. Available from : http://www.bpatc.org.bd/images/document/383_Annual%20Report_2018-19_Final.pdf.
- Bryson, J., & George, B. (2020). Strategic Management in Public Administration. In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Public Administration*. Oxford : Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.1396>.
- Carpenter, R. C. (2005, June). Children and women are the most vulnerable group of the society. *International Studies Quarterly*, 49(2), 295-334. Available from : <http://www.jstor.com/stable/3693516>.

- Chapman, R. A. (1993). Ethics in Public Service. In R. A. Chapman, Twelve Ethics in Public Service (pp. 155-172). Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press. Available from : <http://www.jstor.com/stable/10.3366/j.ctvxcr53.17>.
- Chowdhury, F. D. (2013). Women's Participation in Local Governments in Bangladesh and India. In The Impact of Women's Political Leadership on Democracy and Development: Case Studies from Commonwealth (pp. 64-90). London, UK: Commonwealth Secretariat.
- Clarke, T., & Clegg, S. (1999, December). Changing Paradigms in Public Service Management. *Administrative Theory & Praxis*, 21(4). Available from : <http://www.jstor.com/stable/25611388>.
- Frank, S. A., & Lewis, G. B. (2004, March). Government Employees: Working Hard or Hardly Working? The American Review of Public Administration, 34(1), 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074003258823>.
- GoB. (2012). National Integrity Strategy of Bangladesh. Dhaka: Cabinet Division, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., & Anderson, R. (2010). Multivariate Data Analysis (7th ed.). New York: Pearson.
- Halim, A. (2008). Constitution, Constitutional law and Politics: Bangladesh Perspectives: a Comparative Study of Problems of Constitutionalism in Bangladesh (4 ed.). Dhaka: CCB Foundation.
- Hossain, M., & Islam, M. (2020). Assessing Civil Officers' Knowledge and Capacity on APA, CC, GRS, NIS and RTI to ensure Good Governance for Better Public Service Delivery in Public Administration in Bangladesh. Savar, Dhaka: Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre.
- Huselid, M., Jackson, S. E., & Schuler, R. S. (1997). Technical and Strategic Human Resource Management Effectiveness as Determinants of Firm Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 4(1), 171-188.
- Islam, M. T., Talukder, A. K., Siddiqui, M. N., & Islam, T. (2020, October 14). Tackling the COVID-19 pandemic: The Bangladesh perspective. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.4081/jphr.2020.1794>.
- Islam, M. Z., & Hosen, S. (2021, June 23). An Effectiveness Study on Policy Level Training Course: A Case from Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre, Bangladesh. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 18(3), 41-52. <https://doi.org/10.9734/AJESS/2021/v18i330444>.
- Islam, M. Z., Arifuzzaman, S. M., & Fatema, N. (2012, May). Training Module/Curriculum and Training Effectiveness: An Empirical evidence from Foundation Training Course at BPATC in Bangladesh. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 15-30.
- Islam, Z., & Hossain, R. (2019). What Matters for the Effectiveness of a Training Organization? Evidence from Bpatc. *Journal of Community Positive Practices*, XIX(4), 28-45. <https://doi.org/10.35782/JCPP.2019.4.03>.
- Khan, M. I. (2012). The Impact of Training and Motivation on Performance of Employees. *Business review*, 7(2), 84-95.
- Kirkpatrick, D. (1996). Revisiting Kirkpatrick's four-level-model. *Training & Development*, 1, 54-57.
- Kouzes, A. (2010). Integrity in Public Affairs. *Public Administration Review*, 70(2), 503-506. Retrieved from: <http://www.jstor.com/stable/40606410>.
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the Measurement of Attitudes. *Archives of Psychology*, 22(140), 1-55.
- Lindsey, A., King, E., Hebl, M., & Levine, N. (2015, September). The Impact of Method, Motivation, and Empathy on Diversity Training Effectiveness. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 30(3), 605-617. Available from : <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24634444>.

- Mitchell, S. (1996, May). Gender and Development: A SAFE Recipe. *Development in Practice*, 140-143. Available from : <http://www.jstor.com/stable/4028977>.
- Moniruzzaman, M. (2009, February). Parliamentary Democracy in Bangladesh: An Evaluation of the Parliament during 1991–2006. *Commonwealth and Comparative Politics*, 47(1), 100-126.
- Parliament, B. (1972). Functions and Procedures of Parliament. Available from : www.parliament.gov.bd. <https://www.parliament.gov.bd/index.php/en/about-parliament2/functions-and-procedures-of-parliaments>.
- Perloff, R. M. (2016). *The Dynamics of Persuasion: Communication and Attitudes in the Twenty-First Century*. (6th, Ed.) Routledge.
- Pink, R. (2012, June). Child rights, water rights and human security. *Health and Human Rights*, 4(1), 7887. Available from : <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/healhumarigh.14.1.78>.
- Powell, D. J. (2011, April 8). Supervisor Support. Available from : www.scontrinopowell.com. <https://scontrino-powell.com/>.
- Salah, M. R. (2016). The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity “A case Study of Jordanian Private Sector transportation companies located in the Southern region of Jordan. A particular reference is made to the Govern ate of Maan”. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 5(7), 36-60.
- Samwel, D. J. (2018, January). Impact of Employee Training on Organizational Performance – Case Study of Drilling Companies in Geita, Shinyanga and Mara Regions in Tanzania. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 6(1), 36-41. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/23490349.0601005>.
- Secretariat, C. (2020). Bangladesh : Constitution and politics. Available from : <https://thecommonwealth.org>: <https://thecommonwealth.org/our-membercountries/bangladesh/constitution-politics>.
- Smidt, A., Balandin, S., Sigafos, J., & A.Reed, V. (2009). The Kirkpatrick model: A useful tool for evaluating training outcomes. *Journal of Intellectual & Developmental Disability*, 34(3), 266-274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13668250903093125>.
- UN. (2013). *Human Resources Management and Training*. New York; Geneva: United Nations Economic Commission For Europe. Available from : https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/publications/HRMT_w_cover_resized.pdf.
- UN. (2015). About the Sustainable Development Goals. United Nations. Available from : <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-developmentgoals/#:~:text=The%20Sustainable%20Development%20Goals%20are,environmental%20degrad%20ation%2C%20peace%20and%20justice>.
- Whitfield, D. (2001). A New Public Service Management. In D. Whitfield, *Public Services or Corporate Welfare: Rethinking the Nation State in the Global Economy* (pp. 253-283). Pluto Press. Available from : <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt18fs9c1.16>.
- Wilson, J. E. (2007). Early Colonial India beyond Empire. *The Historical Journal*, 50(4), 951-970. Available from : <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20175135>.